

Cognitive Styles and Academic Performance in English Language Among Public Senior Secondary School Students in Rivers State

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Abstract

This study investigated cognitive styles and academic performance in English language among public senior secondary school students in Rivers State. The correlational research design was adopted for the study. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consisted of 63,846 secondary school one (SS1) students from three hundred and eleven (311) public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The sample size of the study was 480 senior secondary school one (SS1) students selected through the multistage sampling procedure. Self-structured questionnaires titled 'Cognitive Styles Questionnaire (CSQ)' and 'English Language Performance Test (ELPT)' was used in data collection. The instruments for data collection (CSQ and ELPT) were validated by three experts in Educational Psychology, Measurement and Evaluation, and English Language. The reliability of the CSQ was determined using the test-retest method. The reliability of the English Language Performance Test (ELPT) was determined using Kuder-Richardson 20 estimates. The instrument yielded reliability coefficients of reflective cognitive style (.82), impulsive cognitive style sub-scale (.84), and convergent cognitive style sub-scale (.81). The English Language Performance Test (ELPT) yielded a reliability co-efficient of .86. Simple regression analysis was used in answering the research questions and in testing the corresponding null hypotheses at .05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that reflective cognitive style significantly predicted students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that teachers should provide opportunities using cognitive styles for learners to engage in activities that allow for thoughtful analysis.

Keywords: Cognitive Styles, Reflective Cognitive Style, Academic Performance, Impulsive Cognitive Style, Convergent Cognitive Style, English Language, Analytic Cognitive Style, Public, Senior Secondary, School, Students, Rivers State, Nigeria.

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INTRODUCTION

Academic performance of a learner is an indication of the extent to which students have gained mastery of the knowledge, skills and competencies taught in the school system. Academic performance refers to the achievement outcome that shows the extent to which a learner or a student enrolled in a school system attains a specific goal which is the focus of activities of its instructional environment (Anieribi et al., 2022). Academic performance is the outcome of education and learning as it indicates the extent to which the student, teacher, curricular and indeed the educational institutions have achieved the predetermined educational goals. Lamas (2017) in Anieribi et al. (2022) posited that the relevance of academic performance is not only in achievement of educational and learning goals but also necessary for transformation.

Steinmayr et al. (2019) opined that academic performance is a complex factor that encompasses performance outcome in the cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains indicating the extent to which a learner has accomplished specific goals linked to the different domains of learning taught at school. This is to say that it can be measured by self-report by the students on their cognitive, affective and psychomotor outcomes in their academic endeavor. Academic performance is different from the academic potentials of an individual. The former measures a relatively permanent change in an individual's behaviour due to the experiences acquired. Generally, academic performance is a thing of concern to educationists and educational researchers. This is because it determines learner's success in formal education, which can be measured through observations, interview, rating scale and test with numerous variables exerting influence. Though the desire of stakeholders of education is for maximal academic performance of students, the fact remains that poor academic performance has been witnessed among many students and a thing of concern (Oyinvi & Ojimajo, 2020).

Education plays a significant role in manpower development of any country, whether developed or developing countries. Education is a force for all forms of human development, as it manipulates the human intelligence and abilities through its formal and informal settings that results in better knowledge acquisition, values, attitudinal change and skilled oriented activities (Ajoku & Oji, 2020). Asuru (2017) noted that education is a potent instrument for imparting scientific and technological skills as well as liberate the minds of the individual. Education helps in training of the mind to gain knowledge, acquire skills, attitudes and values for the development of man and the nation. This implies that it is a necessary tool for both human and societal development (Nyewusira, 2015). In Nigeria, secondary education serves as a link between primary and higher education. It is assumed that the quality of outputs or products of secondary education determines that of entrants into institutions of higher learning. The quality of products or outputs from secondary education is premised on their academic performance in various subjects offered in senior secondary school certificate examination (SSCE).

At the secondary level of education, there are compulsory subjects that students must offer because of their status in the curriculum, not minding whether such students are in science, commercial, arts or social science class. These are English language, Mathematics, Data processing, Marketing and one of Nigerian languages. Out of these subjects, English language is very essential for students to gain admission into institutions of higher learning. The importance of English language acquisition for proficiency in other school subjects cannot be overemphasized. This is because there is hardly any school subject that the instructions are not written in English in Nigeria. This expertise in the English language is very important and may guarantee success in other subjects. Acquiring sufficient knowledge of English language is

important for educational, economic and national development of a nation. In recognition of the relevance of English language for enhancing educational attainment as well as for improving communication ability of citizens, the subject has become a core subject in the school curriculum (Federal Government of Nigeria, FGN, 2014). For instance, as a prerequisite for university admission, it is compulsory for students to pass the English language at credit level. This also explains why many parents are determined to see their children pass at credit level and above in English language.

Academic performance of secondary school students in Rivers State has remained a source of concern to educators, the society and researchers as well, particularly as the academic performance of secondary school students seems to be in a declined state. Olusegun (2012) in Akuezuilo et al., (2022) reported that less than 40 percent of the candidates who sat for public examination in Nigeria obtained up to credit passes in five subjects which are the minimum academic qualifications for admission into tertiary institutions in Nigeria almost every year. This was further buttressed in a report which revealed that a handful of the examination candidates representing 49.98 percent obtained credits and above in their annually West African Examination Council (Akuezuilo et al., 2022). This further revealed a fluctuation and decline in the performance of students when compared with that of 2018 which was 52.97 percent (West African Examination Council, WAEC, 2020). Academic performance in English language is described as fair and seems to compare favourably to those of the previous years. The public persistent outcry over the declining state of education particularly in Rivers State is most prominent following the annual release of the West African Examination Council (WAEC) results (Nkpordee & Ibinabo, 2022). Romanus (2024) reported that there was a persistent mass failure of students in English language examinations at the secondary school level and that it posed a critical challenge to the education system. Despite the importance of English proficiency for academic advancement and future opportunities, a significant proportion of students consistently perform poorly in English language. Many students struggle to achieve passing grades in English language examinations, hindering their overall performance in English language (Romanus, 2024). Poor performance in English language may restrict students' access to higher education institutions and scholarship opportunities. Komolafe and Yara (2010) in Olagbaju (2020) posited that students' performance in English, as revealed in various examinations in both the subject and other subjects examined in the English language, is still very low. WAEC Chief Examiners' report (2018) in Olagbaju (2020) identified poor writing skill as one of the factors responsible for the perennial poor performance of students in English language. Similarly, Kolawole (1997) in Olagbaju (2020) submitted that any candidate that desires to do well in English language must do well in aspects of the English language examination that assess the writing skills of the candidate such as essay or letter writing, comprehension passage, and summary writing.

In actualization of this fact, scholars such as Fakeye (1999) and Komolafe and Yara (2010) in Olagbaju (2020) to mention just a few worked on improving the quality of instruction in composition writing while Fakeye (2008) and Adebisi (2012) in Olagbaju (2020) worked on English comprehension. Although these studies provided remarkable insights which have impacted classroom practices in the different aspects of the English language, especially in public examinations, has remained generally low. This reveals that there are other factors that contribute to students' poor performance in English examinations apart from the choice of instructional strategy.

From the above, it can be inferred that most of the studies aimed at improving students' performance in English have largely focused on investigating the effectiveness of instructional strategies with little or no attention to learner-related factors in the process of teaching and learning.

Statement of the Problem

Academic performance in English Language has remained a major concern in Nigerian secondary schools, particularly in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. English Language is not only a core subject but also the medium of instruction across all subjects, making proficiency in it crucial for students' academic success and future educational opportunities. Despite many interventions such as curriculum reforms, teacher training programs, and the provision of instructional resources, students' performance in English Language continues to fall below national expectations as reflected in West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) results and internal school assessments.

Research has concertedly suggested that individual differences in learners, such as cognitive styles, may significantly influence academic performance. Cognitive style refers to the preferred way in which individuals perceive, process, and organize information. Divergent, analytic, and holistic cognitive styles, in particular, shape how students approach learning tasks, engage with instructional content, and respond to assessment activities. However, instructional practices in many public schools often do not account for these diverse cognitive preferences, potentially disadvantaging learners whose styles are not aligned with traditional teaching methods.

In Rivers State, limited empirical studies have examined how these cognitive styles influence students' academic performance in English Language. Therefore, understanding this relationship is essential for designing instructional strategies that accommodate students' diverse learning preferences. Consequently, this study seeks to investigate the influence of divergent, analytic, and holistic cognitive styles on academic performance in English Language among public senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The major aim of the study was to investigate cognitive styles and academic performance in English language among public senior secondary school students in Rivers State. In specific terms, the study intended to achieve the following:

- Determine the extent to which reflective cognitive style predicts students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- Examine the extent to which impulsive cognitive style predicts students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- Investigate the extent to which convergent cognitive style predicts students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were stated to guide the study:

- To what extent does reflective cognitive style predict students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
- To what extent does impulsive cognitive style predict students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
- To what extent does convergent cognitive style predict students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were stated to give direction to the study testable at .05 level of significance:

- Reflective cognitive style does not significantly predict students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- Impulsive cognitive style does not significantly predict students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- Convergent cognitive style does not significantly predict students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Cognitive Styles

Humans are the most cognitive organisms in the universe. They receive information outside and within their bodies, interpret the information through the activities of their brains, give meanings to a variety of information their brains come into contact with. Humans all over the world are quite knowledgeable in comparison to other animals because they obtain environmental information as well as information emanating from their bodies, process the information and utilize it for the solution of their problems (Nnachi, 2020). Human beings get, process, store and utilize information. Human beings get information by means of sensation. They interpret the information by means of perception. By means of the two phenomena, we get to know the operations of things in the world by cognitive means.

The word 'Cognition' is derived from the Latin word *cognoscere* meaning "to know" or "to come to know". Thus cognition includes the activities and processes concerned with the acquisition, storage, retrieval and processing of knowledge. In other words, it includes the processes that help us to perceive, attend, remember, think, categorise, reason, decide and soon. Nnachi (2018) defined cognition as the process of knowing through sensation and mental restructuring to create the awareness of the environmental circumstances and be able to make judgement between right and wrong. Colman (2014) in Ikediashi (2018) described cognition as the mental activation involved in acquiring and processing information. Cognition is the process of knowing that involves the reception of raw sensory information and the transformation, elaboration, storage, recovery and use of the information. Cognition depends on the workings of the nervous system and is directly concerned about how we come to know our world, our environment and the workings of things in our world (Nnachi, 2020).

Cognitive style is a psychological concept that emphasizes the fact that individuals perceive and process information differently (Olagbaju, 2020). In the course of learning or acquiring new knowledge, learners come in contact with information and their cognitive style determines the most consistent way that they perceive, process, or utilize the information that they are exposed to. Learners confront learning tasks with different unique qualities or attributes which can be physical, social and intellectual, and these qualities play very important roles in their learning. Zeeb (2004) in Olaobaju (2020) maintained that cognitive style determines how individuals perceive, receive, and process information. A mismatch in learner's cognitive style and the teacher's teaching style in classroom instruction has serious implications for students' academic performance (Olagbaju, 2020). Therefore, it is important for teachers or educators to pay attention to understanding the way students learn or process information.

Several definitions of cognitive style have been provided. Ifelumi (2019) defined cognitive style as the individual differences in the way individuals think, reason, remember, understand situations and translate such situations for problem-solving. Abubakar (2016) defined cognitive style as the relatively stable strategies, preferences and attitudes which determine an individual's typical modes of perceiving, remembering and problem-solving. Arisi (2011) in Eriba et al. (2021) defined cognitive styles as psychological constructs which describe individuals' mode of information perception, organization and presentation. Cognitive style describes a person's typical mode of thinking, remembering or problem-solving. Cognitive style involves individual differences in thought processes, thinking, remembering, perceptions and cognitive performance. Cognitive style is the manner by which individuals perceive information in the environment and the patterns of thought that they use to develop a knowledge base about the world around them.

Students come into the classroom and learning situations with their individual traits as well as diverse unique characteristics. These unique characteristics play very important roles in their learning. Students differ in their choice of perception, processing, and making use of information during teaching and learning encounters and this has been referred to as cognitive style (Fakeye, 2018 in Olagbaju, 2020). An individual's cognitive style is his or her consistent way of responding to, interpreting, and using stimuli in the context of learning. Therefore, cognitive style is not really concerned with what learners want to learn; rather, it is the unconscious cognitive processes involved in the way they learn.

In addition, cognitive style dimensions are personality traits consistently displayed or adopted by individuals over a period of time for processing information. Many of these traits have been identified by scholars as empirically stable forms of information-seeking behaviour (Olagbaju, 2020). Cognitive style is both innate and habitual approach to processing information especially when one is exposed to tasks such as problem-solving, thinking, perceiving and remembering. People learn and process information in different ways; therefore, there are different cognitive style dimensions.

Stapa (2003) in Olagbaju (2020) posited that teaching effectiveness is incomplete without the knowledge of certain learners' traits such as cognitive style and learning performances. Some of the common cognitive style dimensions are field dependent/independent, field divergent/convergent, holistic/analytic and reflective/impulsive. However, the focus of this research work is on reflective/impulsive, divergent/ convergent and analytic /holistic cognitive style dimensions.

Academic Performance

Academic performance is the outcome of evaluating educational objectives. This involves the processes of recording all the cognitive activities of the learner through an agreeable gradation that covers the different levels of emotional and educational activities (Eneremadu & Orji, 2020). It could be seen as the extent to which the learner has achieved his/her educational goals within a given time frame. Varma (2017) asserted that academic performance is an indicator of how much knowledge and skills the learner has obtained from different school subjects. Academic performance refers to the knowledge attained and designated by marks, assigned by teacher (Narad & Abdullah, 2016). In educational context, academic performance is the educational goal to be achieved by a student, teacher or institution over a certain period and is measured either by examinations or continuous assessments and the goal may be different from one individual or institution to another. Academic performance is the outcome of education, the extent to which a student, teacher or institution has achieved their educational goals (Narad & Abdullah, 2016). Academic performance is a measure of the level of student understanding of a subject, which is given after students go through the learning process within a certain period of time and is expressed in the form of grades (Munjirin, et al., 2023). The success of the learning process is indicated by academic performance that satisfies students, focusing on the results achieved.

Academic performance is important because it is the result of an evaluation of the process of educational activities, although high academic performance does not necessarily guarantee the high quality of education (Munjirin, et al., 2023). So, academic performance is an ability that is knowledge (cognitive), attitude (affective) and skills (psychomotor) obtained through the learning process. Salami (2018) noted that academic performance is frequently defined in terms of examination performance. It refers to what skills the student has learned as is usually measured through an assessment like standardized tests, performance assessments and portfolio assessment.

The enhancement and improvement of these skills and knowledge for the learner, therefore, becomes one of the most important objectives of every educational system. The reason is that academic performance is of great importance to the students, teachers, government, parents and the society at large. Academic performance is a yardstick used to measure or determine how far a student has mastered a course of study within a given period. It is a veritable tool that can be used to determine and predict the standard of educational system in Nigeria in terms of its efficiency and effectiveness (Anunaobi & Inko-Tariah, 2020). It portrays the quality of education offered in Nigeria. Unfortunately, the poor academic performance of students has become one of the major concerns of Nigeria as well as the globe (Musa et al., 2018). It has been reported that there is a steady decline in students' academic performance due to so many schools and non-school related demands and responsibilities (Ugoji, 2008 in Eneremadu & Orji, 2020). The phenomenon of poor performance in external examinations among Nigerian students, especially those in senior secondary schools is a matter that has become a source of worry to successive governments and major stakeholders in the education sector in the country (Amalu & Okon, 2018). The performance of many students in an external examination such as West Africa School Certificate (WASC), National Examination Council (NECO), and Junior Secondary School Certificate (JSSC) has been perceived to be poor (Ebenuwa-Okoh, 2015).

A distinction is made between academic performance and academic achievement. Academic performance is the educational attainment of a learner in a specific area or subject. Academic achievement is the total sum of the aggregate performance that is graded. It is the total

level of attainment of an individual. Iwundu (2019) defined academic performance as the achievement of a student in terms of grand aggregate obtained in a test or examination in specific subjects and academic achievement as the degree or level of success attained at the end of an academic endeavour. Iwundu (2019) noted that the yardstick for measuring one's level of academic achievement is by assessing the academic performance of the individual through tests and systematic observation. On regular basis, teachers evaluate students in various ways such as assignments, tests and examinations in order to determine how well or how bad each student performs. Records of academic performance of students are necessary for various reasons such as helping the teacher identify areas that the student needs improvement, helping the student to know his/her areas of weakness so as to work harder towards improving on them, ensure adequate ranking of students on a numerical scale based on their performance so that suspicion and complaints against teachers and schools are minimized (Bell, 2018).

Olufemi et al. (2018) provided that students' performance is affected by several factors which include students' learning skills, parental background, peer influence, teachers' quality, learning infrastructure among others. Since learning is an integral aspect and a major determinant of academic performance, it logically follows that the factors influencing learning in an individual may have direct or covert influence on the individual's academic performance. Family factors or school factors may largely determine academic performance of students. There is also some form of relationship between cognitive skills, learning styles and academic performance of the students. A student who finds it difficult to receive, store and retrieve information may not perform well in academics. Also, a student may not perform optimally when he or she is using the inappropriate learning style in the learning process.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Riding and Cheema Cognitive Styles Analysis (1991)

Richard Riding and Indra Cheema developed the Wholist-Analytic and Verbal-Imagery Model that describes two dimensions of cognitive styles: The Wholist-Analytic (W-A) dimension and the Verbal-Imagery (V-I) dimension (Lusweti et al., 2018). The Wholist-Analytic dimension describes how individuals tend to organize information; either in wholes or in discrete parts. The dimension acknowledges that some individuals process and organize information into its component parts (described as analytics); while others retain a global, or overall view of information (described as wholists). The analytic learner is described as one who treats a situation as a collection of parts and tends to focus on one or two aspects of the situation at a time to the exclusion of the others. The wholist learner on the other hand, treats a situation as a whole and tends to have an overall perspective and to appreciate its total context.

Riding and Cheema (1991) in Lusweti et al. (2018) posited that the Wholist-Analytic dimension interacts with the structure and organization of contents of instruction. For example, analytics take a structured approach to learning and will prefer information that is set out in a clearly organized way. They may impose order of information, events and experiences, which are not inherently structured, or may attempt to do so in situations where structuring is appropriate. Wholists on the other hand will not take a structured approach and may therefore need help in imposing a structure on some unstructured situations or experiences.

The second dimension described by Riding and Cheema (1991) in Lusweti et al., (2017) was the Verbal-Imagery (V-I) dimension. The V-I dimension describes an individual's habitual

mode of representation of information in memory during thinking. Verbalisers consider the information they read, see or listen to, in words or verbal associations. Imagers, on the other hand, as they read, listen to or consider information, they experience fluent spontaneous and frequent pictorial mental pictures. The V-I discussion focuses on mode of presentation of information. Verbalisers prefer textual modes of presentation while imagers prefer pictorial and diagrammatic information.

The rationale of this theory is that this theory can be applied in the classroom to promote teaching and learning to help students learn to their highest potential. Teachers can teach wholists and analytics effectively in class by creating a supportive and stimulating environment that allows these learners to perceive and process information or learning experiences in the classroom.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a correlational research design. The study was conducted in Rivers State, Nigeria. Rivers State is located in the South-South geopolitical zone and is characterized by ethnic diversity, economic vibrancy, and a large population of school-age children. The state has 23 Local Government Areas and 311 public senior secondary schools distributed across riverine and upland communities. The focus of the study was on students in public senior secondary schools, who were considered suitable due to their literacy level and ability to respond accurately to research instruments.

The population of the study comprised 63,846 Senior Secondary School One (SS1) students drawn from 311 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State during the 2022/2023 academic session. The population consisted of 30,440 male and 33,406 female students across the 23 Local Government Areas of the state.

The sample size for the study was 480 SS1 students selected from twelve (12) Local Government Areas across the three senatorial districts of Rivers State. The minimum sample size of 400 was determined using Taro Yamane's formula; however, this was increased to 480 to enhance representativeness and robustness of findings.

A multistage sampling technique was employed. First, the state was stratified into three senatorial districts. Four Local Government Areas were randomly selected from each district. Five public senior secondary schools were then randomly selected from each Local Government Area. Finally, eight SS1 students were randomly selected from each sampled school to make up the study sample.

Two instruments were used for data collection: the Cognitive Styles Questionnaire (CSQ) and the English Language Performance Test (ELPT). The CSQ was a self-structured questionnaire designed on a four-point Likert scale ranging from Very High Extent (4) to Very Low Extent (1). It consisted of sections on students' bio-data, cognitive styles, learning styles, and self-efficacy.

The instruments were validated by experts in Measurement and Evaluation, Educational Psychology, and English Language to ensure face and content validity. Reliability of the CSQ was established using the test-retest method and Pearson Product Moment Correlation, yielding coefficients ranging from .81 to .84 across sub-scales. The ELPT reliability was determined using Kuder-Richardson Formula 20, yielding a coefficient of .86. These values were considered adequate for the study.

The instruments were administered directly to the respondents with the assistance of teachers and research assistants after obtaining permission from school principals. All 480 copies administered were successfully retrieved. Simple linear regression analysis was used to answer the research questions and test the null hypotheses at the .05 level of significance. Data analysis was carried out using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 29.

RESULTS

Research Question One: To what extent does reflective cognitive style predict students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypothesis One: Reflective cognitive style does not significantly predict students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 1: Summary of Simple Linear Regression Model of Reflective Cognitive Style on Students' Academic Performance in English Language

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.755 ^a	.570	.563	3.4104		
ANOVA Associated with Simple Regression						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-value	P-value
Regression		3062.1450	1	3062.145	86.192	.000
Residual		16981.826	98	35.527		
Total		20043.971	99			

a. Dependent Variable: Academic Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Reflective Cognitive Style

Table 1 showed the model summary of reflective cognitive style on students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The simple linear regression model gave a coefficient of .755, R^2 of .570 and adjusted R^2 of .563. This showed that reflective cognitive style accounted for 57% variation in the students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This therefore indicated that to a high extent, reflective cognitive style predicted students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Again, the table also revealed the results of ANOVA associated with simple regression which yielded an F-value of 86.192 gotten at degree of freedom between 1 and 98 with its corresponding P-value of 0.000 which is less than the chosen level of significance ($p < 0.05$). The null hypothesis is rejected. It therefore, indicated that, reflective cognitive style significantly predicted students' academic performance in English Language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question Two: To what extent does impulsive cognitive style predict students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypothesis Two: Impulsive cognitive style does not significantly predict students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 2: Summary of Simple Linear Regression Model of Impulsive Cognitive Style on Students' Academic Performance in English Language

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.744 ^a	.553	.551	3.3502		
ANOVA Associated with Simple Regression						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-value	P-value
Regression		3211.2450	1	3211.245	88.635	.000
Residual		17318.123	53	36.230		
Total		20529.368	54			

a. Dependent Variable: Academic Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Impulsive Cognitive Style

Table 2 showed the model summary of impulsive cognitive style on students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The simple linear regression model gave a coefficient of .744, R^2 of .553 and adjusted R^2 of .551. This shows that impulsive cognitive style accounted for 55% variation in the students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This therefore implied that to a high extent, impulsive cognitive style predicted students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Again, the table also revealed the results of ANOVA associated with simple regression which yielded an F-value of 88.635 gotten at degree of freedom between 1 and 53 with its corresponding P-value of 0.000 which is less than the chosen level of significance ($p < 0.05$). The null hypothesis is rejected. It therefore, indicated that, impulsive cognitive style significantly predicted students' academic performance in English Language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question Three: To what extent does convergent cognitive style predict students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypothesis Three: Convergent cognitive style does not significantly predict students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 3: Summary of Simple Linear Regression Model of Convergent Cognitive Style on Students' Academic Performance in English Language

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.780 ^a	.608	.605	3.6157		
ANOVA Associated with Simple Regression						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-value	P-value
Regression		2341.4561	1	2341.456	68.880	.000
Residual		16247.113	107	33.989		
Total		18588.569	108			

a. Dependent Variable: Academic Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Convergent Cognitive Style

Table 3 showed the model summary of convergent cognitive style on students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The simple

linear regression model gave a coefficient of .780, R^2 of .608 and adjusted R^2 of .605. This showed that convergent cognitive style accounted for 61% variation in the students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This therefore indicated that to a high extent, convergent cognitive style predicted students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Furthermore, the table also revealed the results of ANOVA associated with simple regression which yielded an F-value of 68.880 gotten at degree of freedom between 1 and 107 with its corresponding P-value of .000 which is less than the chosen level of significance ($p < .05$). The null hypothesis is rejected. It therefore, indicated that, convergent cognitive style significantly predicted students' academic performance in English Language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Reflective Cognitive Style and Students' Academic Performance

Table 1 of research question one shows that, the extent to which reflective cognitive style predicts students' academic performance in English Language is high in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, while the result of the corresponding hypothesis indicated that reflective cognitive style significantly predicts students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

This finding is in agreement with the study of Mark (2015) who found that reflective cognitive style significantly predicted academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State. This result could be probably because students with reflective cognitive style analyze different aspects of a problem before arriving at a solution. This thorough approach can lead to a deeper understanding of the material and more accurate answers, which enhances academic performance of students.

Okoro (2017) also found that reflective cognitive style significantly predicted academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Enugu State. This present finding could be because reflective thinking encourages students to evaluate arguments, identify biases and consider the validity of various sources of information.

Clarkson (2019) also revealed that reflective cognitive style significantly predicted academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Lagos State, which is consistent with the present study. Similarly, reflective students tend to develop more effective study habits. They are more likely to engage in active learning techniques such as summarizing information, creating concept maps, and self-testing, which are linked to better retention and understanding of the material.

Karthik (2019) also collaborated that reflective cognitive style significantly predicted academic performance of public secondary school students in India. This result could be probably because reflective cognitive students often feel more prepared and confident due to their thorough preparation, which can reduce test anxiety. Lower anxiety levels can lead to better performance on examination and other high-stakes assessments, thereby promoting academic performance of students.

Impulsive Cognitive Style and Students' Academic Performance

Table 2 of research question two shows that, the extent to which impulsive cognitive style predict students' academic performance in English Language is high in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, while the result of the corresponding hypothesis two indicated that impulsive cognitive style significantly predicts students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

This is in accordance with the study of Matthew (2016) who found that impulsive cognitive style significantly predicted academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Delta State. This result is probably because impulsive thinkers often demonstrate high levels of creativity and innovation. Their willingness to take risks and think outside the box can lead to original ideas, solutions and academic performance

Lawson (2018) revealed that impulsive cognitive style significantly predicted academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State. This is probably because impulsive students are often more willing to participate actively in classroom discussions and activities. Their spontaneous contributions can enrich classroom dynamics and foster a more engaging learning environment for all students, resulting in academic performance.

Chang (2018) also found that impulsive cognitive style significantly related to academic performance of public senior secondary school students in Rivers State, which is consistent with the present study. Horwood (2021) also supported that impulsive cognitive style significantly relate to academic performance in Chemistry of high school students in New Zealand. This is probably because impulsive students act quickly on feedback provided by teachers, applying suggestions immediately rather than delaying implementation. This can lead to rapid improvements in their work and learning processes.

Convergent Cognitive Style and Students' Academic Performance

Table 3 of research question three shows that, the extent to which convergent cognitive style predicts students' academic performance in English Language is high in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State; while the result of the corresponding hypothesis indicated that convergent cognitive style significantly predict students' academic performance in English language in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

This finding is in harmony with the study of Ozoji and Kolo (2017) who found that convergent cognitive style predicted academic performance in mathematics of public senior secondary school students in Oyo State. This finding could be probably because convergent thinkers often develop systematic and organized study habits. They are likely to create structured study plans, use detailed notes, and follow methodical approaches to learning and revision, which can lead to better retention and understanding of material.

Oluwatola and Lawrence (2016) also revealed that convergent cognitive influenced academic performance in Biology of secondary school students in Lagos State. This could be because convergent cognitive style helps students to build a solid foundation in core concepts. Their focus on mastering fundamental principles and applying them correctly ensures a deep and robust understanding of essential subject matter.

Eyesenck et al. (2020) also collaborated that convergent cognitive influenced academic achievement in English Language of college students in New Jersey. This result could be

because convergent thinkers are skillful at breaking down complex information into manageable parts and analyzing it systematically, which in turn result to improved academic performance.

CONCLUSION

The study investigated the relationship between cognitive styles and academic performance in English language among public senior secondary school students in Rivers State. The findings revealed that students' cognitive styles significantly influenced their performance, with analytical and reflective learners demonstrating higher achievement in English language tasks. This has suggested that students' preferred ways of processing information affect comprehension, retention, and application of language skills. The results emphasized the importance of recognizing cognitive diversity in the classroom, as tailoring instructional strategies to accommodate different cognitive styles enhances learning outcomes. Educators are encouraged to employ varied teaching methods, including interactive, reflective, and practical approaches, to engage all learners effectively. Thus, cognitive styles into teaching practices improve academic performance, stimulate learner confidence, and promote effective English language mastery, and contributing positively to overall educational development in Rivers State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, discussion and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- Since the reflective cognitive style predicts students' academic performance in English language, teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria should purposefully incorporate instructional strategies that promote reflection such as guided reading, essay writing, peer review and think-aloud activities that allow students adequate time to analyze language tasks before responding.
- Since impulsive cognitive style also predicts students' academic performance in English language, teachers should adopt classroom practices that help impulsive learners improve accuracy without suppressing their spontaneity, which can be achieved through structured activities such as timed reading exercises with feedback, error-analysis tasks and scaffolded speaking and writing activities.
- The predictive influence of convergent cognitive style on students' academic performance in English language requires that curriculum planners and teachers should integrate problem-solving and application-oriented tasks into English language instruction.

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